

Conference Abstract

Beyond the Net: Optimizing eDNA Sampling and Analysis for Challenging Muddy Habitats and the Endangered Weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*)

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Abstract

Elusive and endangered species are prime candidates for environmental DNA (eDNA) monitoring (Duarte et al. 2023). The European weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) is one such species where traditional fishing methods may not yield conclusive results on its presence/absence. On the other hand, eDNA monitoring is less labour-intensive than conventional methods and may require only a small amount of water if species-specific qPCR/ddPCR markers are utilised (Thomsen et al. 2011, Sigsgaard et al. 2015, Kusanke et al. 2020, Brys et al. 2020). We aim to develop a standardised eDNA protocol that would provide additional information to traditional fishing surveys of *Misgurnus*. Such surveys are especially challenging in smaller vegetated waterbodies and wetlands in Central Europe where electrofishing, dip-netting, or fish trapping may not be feasible. As such, these wetland habitats are also among the most neglected European habitats despite facing considerable threats (Šmejkal et al. 2025).

We are currently testing eDNA field sampling procedures and laboratory analyses that will be functional across all known *M. fossilis* haplotypes and tailored to the specific

challenges of muddy-water habitats (e.g., collection farther from shore without stirring up sediment, clogging of filters after filtering small volumes, qPCR inhibition) and their mosaic distribution across the landscape. The latter poses challenges for large-scale monitoring campaigns where maintaining sample storage and transport at sub-zero temperatures in the field may not be possible. Non-frozen samples may be fixated, however, the use of fixatives increases the risk of contamination, limits the volume sampled (e.g., early fixated samples required 35 ml of fixatives (ethanol and sodium acetate) added to 15 ml of water; Ficetola et al. 2008), and such samples may have significantly lower DNA yields (Kusanke et al. 2020). The issues posed by the ethanol-sodium acetate fixation may be alleviated by using other reagents, such as lysis buffers, which allow eDNA preservation even in extreme conditions, e.g., remote localities in arid African savannas (Schenekar et al. 2024).

The optimised protocol should be cost-effective and straightforward enough to be used by citizen science projects. The species-specific markers are primarily optimised to be multiplexed, allowing us to combine multiple markers from a single species to increase the probability of detection (Brys et al. 2023) as well as to simultaneously discriminate other co-occurring fish species, primarily the endangered crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) (Šmejkal et al. 2025). Moreover, multiplexing lowers the cost and handling effort of analyses (Jo et al. 2019) and, by decreasing the necessary volume of eDNA sample used per reaction, increases the number of tests that can be performed on a single sample when DNA extraction volumes are low (Wozney and Wilson 2017). Multiplexing also allows for the addition of an inhibition-sensitive internal positive control (IPC). Further markers—such as those specific to invasive species of *Misgurnus* or *Carassius*—may be included to provide additional information on the current state of the localities in question. eDNA is a valuable tool for early detection of invaders present even at low densities (Jo et al. 2019, Jerde 2019) and, as such, may aid in monitoring invasive Asian weatherfish species, the spread of which is currently of high concern in Europe. Their early detection is crucial, as once established, the removal of invasive weatherfish is extremely challenging—the fish may remain alive buried in sediment for months even when the affected waterbodies are drained (Cano-Barbacid et al. 2025).

Keywords

eDNA, fieldwork, optimisation, fish, *Misgurnus*, *Carassius*, endangered, conservation, monitoring, wetlands

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Grant title

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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